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Press Release N. 1

The newly launched Horizon Europe project **AGRIGEP** has just started at the beginning of 2023

Gödöllő, 07/07/2023

The newly started project **AGRIGEP**, funded by the European Union, had its official start on **January 1st 2023**, and had the kick-off meeting on **February 28th - 1st March** in Gödöllő, hosted by the **Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE)**.

With a total investment of 998,237,50 EUR, **AGRIGEP** brings together **six partners** from **five European countries including Universities, a non-profit organization, and an SME**. Gender inequality is a major barrier in the R&I area that limit the capabilities and capacities of research and education institutions. Although major efforts to reach gender equality (GE) in R&I have been made in many areas of the world, there are still prominent inequalities in the widening countries. Across the EU, the development of Gender Equality Plans (GEP) intends to address the problems at universities and research organisations; however, the variability in capability, capacity, and expertise hinders the efficient implementation of the institutional GEPs. Additionally, there are specific GE issues within certain fields of study at research and education institutions. In this context, GE issues in the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) fields are well-known, and specific action plans have been developed. Within STEM, agriculture and life-science-focused higher education and research institutions face very similar problems, but they lack sector-specific measures and mitigation plans. Furthermore, in agriculture, a large GE sector-specific imbalance exists in developing countries where a relevant proportion of universities' international students come from.

The **AGRIGEP** project, **with the joint efforts of six consortium partners**, will perform a comprehensive assessment of the widening universities' current status of GEP implementation, improving capabilities through intensive capacity building, and developing, and implementing agriculture and life-science targeted GEP with sectorial-specific measures and strategies. These results could lead to long-term institutional reforms. Additionally, this project will work to establish the inclusion of GE issues within the universities' educational system and the professional training of their students, with a special focus on 3rd countries. The realization of these objectives and the implementation of inclusive GEPs will enhance the inclusiveness, reputation, attractiveness, and research excellence of widening country higher education and research institutions. Moreover, it will promote the transformation of institutions and advance GE within the ERA as well.

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The kick-off meeting was launched on February 28th – March 1st, 2023 hosted in Gödöllő, Hungary organized by the Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE) the Coordinator institution.

The meeting was opened by the AGRIGEP Coordinator Institution where the Project Officer (REA) and the Policy officer from the European Commission attended the meeting online.

The main section of the event was about presenting all activities that the consortia will carry out during the lifetime of the project which will be a 3-year program. The AGRIGEP meeting also presented all project partners and team members. The meeting was a 2 days event and 26 participants attended it in person and offline.

AGRIGEP Beneficiaries are:

- Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE), Coordinator,
- Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU),
- University of Primorska (UP),
- Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya - BarcelonaTech (UPC),
- Yellow Window (YW),
- Association of Hungarian Women in Science (NATE),

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Stay tuned for more news on AGRIGEP's upcoming results and learn more about the activities carried out!

Contacts

AGRIGEP Coordination Office

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